

Vocabulary Distribution Overlap

Overlap Coefficient: 0.7702

Vocabulary Distribution Overlap
Overlap Coefficient: 0.7614

Filtered High RF Verbs

Distribution of Relative Frequency Differentials (Δ RF)

Marcus Aurelius vs. Epictetus

Distribution of Relative Frequency Differentials (Δ RF)

Marcus Aurelius vs. Epictetus

Filtered High RF Verbs

